

CONCEPT WOMAN IN THE ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN PHRASEOLOGY (BY THE MATERIAL OF PAROEMIOLOGICAL UNITS)

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Annotation: The article analyses the English and Russian paroemiological units representing the concept WOMAN. The chosen paroemiological units are classified depending on negative or positive connotation of the verbalized concept. The paper aims to reveal the content of the analyzed concept, to identify culturally specific and culturally universal views on a woman in the English and Russian phraseological worldview. The findings indicate that perception of the WOMAN concept differs among the speakers of the English and Russian languages.

Key words: paroemiology; concept; language and thinking; linguistic worldview; phraseology; concept WOMAN.

The issues of language learning in the light of the culture of its native speakers are raised by many outstanding linguists, including B. Wharf, E. Sepir, M. Minsky and many others. So, according to M. Minsky, people are at the mercy of the language in which communication takes place in this language community. The scientist notes that the surrounding world is formed on the basis of language habits peculiar to a particular social group [1, p. 206].

The concept of WOMAN considered in this article seems relevant for study, since it is a universal concept and archetypal for human consciousness. This concept has already been developed in the works of some researchers. Thus, O. A. Chibysheva studies the present concept on the material of subject phraseological units naming a woman [9], the issues of gender categorization within paremiological units are covered by G. Sh. Khakimova [8], in the PhD thesis of V. V. Vasyuk considers the concept of a WOMAN in statics and dynamics on the material of phraseological units of the English language [3]

The scientific novelty of this work consists in the fact that this concept is studied within the framework of paremiology as a component of the phraseological fund of any language, within the framework of the article, the division of paremias into thematic groups is carried out and priority among the marked groups are established. This determines **the relevance** of this work, since the study builds an appropriate fragment of the worldview of the English

and Russian languages, which makes it possible to identify national-specific and common features in the views of a woman in the English and Russian language worldviews. The data obtained during the study can be used to study the concept of a WOMAN in dynamics, when contrasting this concept with other concepts, as well as in the study of other universal concepts.

The purpose of the research is to highlight the negative and positive characteristics of a woman reflected in English and Russian, using the example of selected paremiological units, as well as to establish the national and cultural specifics of the paremias representing and describing the concept of a WOMAN in English and Russian. Russian language's 132 paremiological units and 177 paremiological units, obtained by continuous selection from the dictionaries of English and Russian languages, served as the research material.

The objectives of this work include: to identify paremias with positive and negative connotations using the method of component analysis; to establish priority thematic groups within the framework of positive and negative attitudes towards women and to identify national-specific and common to both languages thematic groups through methods of semantic description and conceptual analysis; using the method of quantitative analysis, to establish dominant thematic groups within the framework of positive and negative characteristics.

During the study, 61 paremia of the English language and 107 paremiological units of the Russian language were identified when selecting units with a positive connotation. In the study of the paremiological fund, paremias that form thematically common subgroups for both languages are noted, but also those units that allow the formation of national-specific subgroups for each language are also noted.

Thus, the following subgroups common to both languages are distinguished (8 subgroups in total):

1. A woman appears to be the keeper of the hearth. Within the framework of the English paremiological fund, 13 paremias were allocated (for example, a wife gives beauty to a house – a woman brings beauty to the house; the wife is the key of the house – a woman is the key to the house) [10; 11], within the framework of the Russian paremiological fund, only 6 paremias with a similar meaning were allocated (for example, such parodies as the house is the mistress; without a wife, the house is sodom) [4].
2. Positive characteristics of the female mind, flexibility of the female mind, female wisdom. This thematic subgroup includes 12 English paroemias (for example, behind every successful man is a woman – behind every successful

man is a woman; the wit of a woman is a great matter – female reason is great wisdom) [10; 11] and 28 Russian paroemias (for example, the women's council is not wise, and who is it he does not listen, he is stupid; a woman's mind is better than any thoughts) [4].

3. A positive characteristic of female modesty. Within this thematic subgroup, 10 English paroemias are singled out (for example, modesty is the beauty of women – modesty adorns a woman; nineteen nay-says of a maiden are half a grant – nineteen refusals from a girl are half consent) [10; 11] and 7 Russian paroemias (humility is a maiden necklace; a girl decorates modesty, not gilded clothes) [4].

4. Positive characteristics of female influence on a man, as well as the importance of a woman in a man's life. This subgroup includes 8 English paremiological units (for example, lady is a woman who makes it easy for a man to be a gentleman – a lady is a woman who helps a man to become a gentleman easily) [10; 11] and 13 Russian ones (such as a good wife and a bad husband will be a good fellow; a good wife and an honest husband; a man without a wife is like a goose without water) [4].

5. Positive description of the role of love and family in a woman's life. Within the framework of this subgroup, only 3 English paroemias are allocated (for example, a woman's place is in the home – a woman's place is at home) [10; 11] and 20 Russian paroemias (a wife without a husband is worse than a widow; without a husband, a wife is always an orphan) [4].

6. Positive characteristic of female kindness. This subgroup is marked by 3 English paroemias (for example, good wife and health is a man's best wealth – a good wife and health is a man's best wealth) [10; 11] and 9 Russian units (to take a good wife – no boredom, no grief to see; a good wife teaches housekeeping, and an evil one from excommunicates at home) [4].

7. Positive characteristic of female diligence. This thematic subgroup includes 2 English paremiological units (a woman's work is never done – there is no end to women's work; men get wealth and women keep it – men get benefits, the hostess saves them) [10; 11] and 12 Russian paremias (choose a wife not in a round dance, but in the garden; the girl is red not by body, but by deed) [4].

8. A positive characteristic of a woman who serves as a "reflection" of her husband. This subgroup is extremely small and is represented by only 2 English paroemias (a good husband makes a good wife – a good husband and a good wife; a good wife makes a good husband – a good wife has a good husband) [10; 11] and 5 Russian units (husband and wife are smeared with one world; husband and wife they are sewn with one bast) [4].

Also, when studying paremiological units reflecting the positive characteristics of women in English and Russian paremiology, national-specific groups characteristic only of a particular linguistic culture were identified. So, for the English paremiological foundation, a subgroup was nationally specific, which includes paremias positively characterizing a cheerful female disposition and external female attractiveness (8 paremias of the English language, for example, a cheerful wife is the joy of life - a cheerful wife is the joy in life; beauty is the wisdom of women – beauty is a woman's wisdom) [10; 11].

When studying the Russian paremiological fund , the following national - specific subgroups were noted:

1. Positive characteristic of a woman's willingness to make sacrifices for love and family (4 Russian paroemias, for example, for the sake of a nice person and I don't feel sorry for myself; at least a cracker with water, if only, dear, with you) [4].

2. A positive characteristic of female strength and endurance (2 units, for example, a woman is not a sourdough: she got up and went; a wife is not a pot, you will not break it).

Thus, the analysis carried out and the statistical data obtained show that in English there is a predominance of paremias with negative connotation (71 paremias with negative connotation a characteristic in contrast to 61 paroemias with a positive description). In the Russian language, on the contrary, the presence of units with a positive connotation prevails (107 paroemias with a positive characteristic in contrast with 70 paroemias of a negative nature). So, it is possible to assert the dominance of the positive description of the concept of WOMAN in Russian and the negative one in English. The study also demonstrates that the thematic description of a woman in both languages occurs in a similar way, while some thematic groups specific to each language are also distinguished.

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